

Supporting information

Primary benzylamines by efficient N-alkylation of benzyl alcohols using commercial Ni catalysts and easy-to-handle ammonia sources

Yongzhuang Liu^{†‡}, Anastasiia Afanasenko[†], Saravanakumar Elangovan[†], Zhuohua Sun[†], Katalin Barta^{*†}

[†]Stratingh Institute for Chemistry, University of Groningen, Nijenborgh 4, 9747 AG, Groningen, The Netherlands.

[‡]Key Laboratory of Bio-Based Material Science and Technology, Ministry of Education, Northeast Forestry University, Harbin 150040, P. R. China

Corresponding author email: k.barta@rug.nl

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1. General methods and procedures

Chromatography and spectroscopy

Column chromatography was performed using Merck silica gel type 9385 230-400 mesh and typically dichloromethane and methanol as eluent.

TLC: Merck silica gel 60, 0.25 mm. The components were visualized by UV or KMnO₄ staining.

Gas Chromatography was used for product identification as well as determination of conversion and selectivity values. Product identification was performed by GC-MS (Shimadzu QP2010 Ultra) with an HP-1MS column, and helium as carrier gas. GC-MS method: The temperature program started at 40 °C for 10 min, heated by 10°C/min to 90 °C and held for 5 min, then heated by 15°C/min to 260 °C and held for 5 min, after heated by 25°C/min to 290 °C and held for 0 min. For Vanillin amine (**2m**) GC-MS method: The temperature program started at 45 °C for 0 min, heated by 12°C/min to 300 °C and held for 10 min.

Conversions and product selectivities were determined by GC-FID (Shimadzu GC-2014) with an HP-5MS column using nitrogen as carrier gas. GC-FID analysis method: The temperature program started at 40 °C for 10 min, heated by 10°C/min to 90 °C and held for 5 min, then heated by 15°C/min to 260 °C and held for 5 min, after heated by 25°C/min to 290 °C and held for 0 min. For Vanillin amine (**2m**) GC-FID analysis method: The temperature program started at 40 °C for 5 min, heated by 10°C/min to 140 °C and held for 10 min, then heated by 10°C/min to 290 °C and held for 0 min.

Mass spectrometry: Mass spectra were recorded on an AEI-MS-902 mass spectrometer (EI⁺) or a LTQ Orbitrap XL (ESI⁺).

NMR spectroscopy: ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian Mercury Plus 400, Agilent MR 400 (400 and 100.59 MHz, respectively) and Bruker Avance NEO 600 (600 and 150.92 MHz, respectively) using CD₃OD as a solvent. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded at room temperature. Chemical shift values are reported in ppm with the solvent resonance as the internal standard (CD₃OD: 3.31 for ¹H, 49.00 for ¹³C). Data are reported as follows: chemical shifts, multiplicity (s = singlet, d = doublet, t = triplet, q = quartet, br. = broad, m = multiplet), coupling constants (Hz), and integration.

Conversion and selectivity calculation

Dodecane was used as an internal standard for calibration. Conversion and selectivity were calculated in the following way:

$$\text{Conversion \%} = \frac{\text{original benzyl alcohol} - \text{remaining benzyl alcohol} / \text{mol}}{\text{original benzyl alcohol} / \text{mol}} \times 100\%$$
$$\text{Selectivity \%} = \frac{\text{obtained benzylamine} / \text{mol}}{\text{original benzyl alcohol} - \text{remaining benzyl alcohol} / \text{mol}} \times 100\%$$

Note 1: control experiments in order to verify the possibility that the components of stainless steel (Cr, Ni, Fe, etc.) contribute to the catalytic process were carried out in the following way.

For Raney Ni catalytic system: 1 mmol benzyl alcohol, 20 μ L dodecane, 3 mL *tert*-amyl alcohol and 0.4 mL aqueous ammonia were added into the Swagelok reactor, the reactor was put into a pre-heated heating block at 180 °C for 18 h, after cooling down, the mixture was analyzed by GC-FID.

For Ni/Al₂O₃-SiO₂ catalytic system: 0.5 mmol vanillyl alcohol, 3 mL *tert*-amyl alcohol and 2 mmol ammonium carbonate were added into the Swagelok reactor, the reactor was put into a pre-heated heating block at 140 °C for 18 h, after cooling the mixture was analyzed by GC-FID. The obtained results displayed no formation of any amine product.

Note 2: in order to determine if leached Ni could have contributed to the reaction: two kinds of experiments were conducted, namely “hot filtration” as well as ICP analysis for both catalytic systems (Raney Ni with aqueous ammonia and Ni/Al₂O₃-SiO₂ with ammonium carbonate).

After the reaction, the reaction mixture was filtered through a micro-filter to remove the catalyst. All solvents were removed using rotary evaporator. Then 7 mL HNO₃ was added to dissolve all the metal components, the mixture was centrifuged to get a clear solution, and analyzed by Perkin Elmer instrument (Optima 7000DV).

“Hot filtration”:

For Raney Ni catalytic system, the experiment was performed as follows: 200 mg Raney Ni, 20 μ L dodecane, 3 mL *tert*-amyl alcohol and 0.2 mL aqueous ammonia were added into the Swagelok reactor. The reactor was put into a pre-heated heating block at 180 °C for 18 h. Then, the reactor was cooled down with ice-water and the catalyst was removed by filtration. The filtrate was put into a new Swagelok reactor, 0.5 mmol benzyl alcohol and 0.2 mL aqueous ammonia were added and reactor was placed back to a pre-heated heating block at 180 °C for another 18 h. After cooling down, the mixture was analyzed by GC-FID.

For Ni/Al₂O₃-SiO₂ catalytic system: 200 mg Ni/Al₂O₃-SiO₂, 3 mL *tert*-amyl alcohol and 1 mmol ammonia carbonate were added into the Swagelok reactor. The reactor was put into a pre-heated heating block at 140 °C for 18 h. After cooling down with ice-water, the catalyst was removed by filtration. The filtrate was put into a new Swagelok reactor, 0.5 mmol vanillyl alcohol and 1 mmol ammonia carbonate were added and reactor was placed back to a pre-heated heating block at 140 °C for 18 h. After cooling down, the mixture was analyzed by GC-FID.

The obtained results revealed that no product formation was detected for both Raney Ni and Ni/Al₂O₃-SiO₂ systems.

ICP analysis:

The Ni content in the liquid solution (filtrate) was analyzed by ICP after reaction for both Raney Ni and Ni/Al₂O₃-SiO₂ catalytic systems. As could be seen from the Table below, no obvious leaching was detected in both catalytic systems. The obtained results additionally confirm the remarkable stability of the employed catalytic systems as well as the possibility for the catalysts recycling.

Catalytic system	Leached Ni from the catalyst / %	Ni concentration in filtrate / ppm	Ni amount in the filtrate / mg
Raney Ni (200 mg, 20% water) & a.q. NH ₃	0.05	24	0.08
Ni/Al ₂ O ₃ -SiO ₂ (200 mg, 65% Ni loading) & (NH ₄) ₂ CO ₃	0.3	144	0.43

Note 3: monitoring the pressure in the reactor during the reaction.

The phase behavior of ammonia gas in the batch reactor is crucial. We used the Parr reactor (10 mL) to check the pressure during the reaction (optimized best condition: typically, 200 mg Raney Ni catalyst, 1 mmol substrate, 0.4 mL aqueous ammonia, 3 mL *p*-xylene, 180 °C and 18 h). The pressure was ~14 bar.

Considering the phase behavior of both *p*-xylene and aqueous ammonia at 180 °C, *p*-xylene is vapor-liquid state, the vapor pressure is around 13 bar.¹ For the aqueous ammonia, the vapor pressure is around 8 bar.² The headspace is composed of vapors of *p*-xylene, water and ammonia. The observed pressure was similar to reported one in Hii's work (12 bar pressure in batch).

2. Experimental section

Scheme S1: Amination of benzyl alcohol with ammonia

Table S1: Screening of different Ni catalysts

Entry	Catalyst	Conversion / %		Selectivity / %		
		1a	2a	3a	3'a	4a+5a
1	Raney Ni	92	43	2	3	52
2	Ni/C	36	71	6	9	14
3	Ni/Al ₂ O ₃ /SiO ₂	100	3	7	0.4	13

General reaction conditions: *General Procedure 1*, 0.5 mmol of **1a**, catalysts (100 mg), a.q. NH₃ (25 wt%, 0.2 mL, 2.6 mmol), 180 °C, 3 mL *t*-amyl alcohol, 18h. Conversion and selectivity were determined by GC-FID using dodecane as an internal standard.

Table S2: Screening of different Raney Ni catalysts

Entry	Catalyst	Conversion / %		Selectivity / %		
		1a	2a	3a	3'a	4a+5a
1	Raney Ni 3202	81	41	3	3	54
2	Raney Ni 4200	88	61	3	2	34
3	Raney Ni 2800	83	61	2	3	35

General reaction conditions: *General Procedure 1*, 1 mmol of **1a**, catalysts (200 mg), a.q. NH₃ (25 wt%, 0.2 mL, 2.6 mmol), 180 °C, 3 mL *p*-xylene, 18h. Conversion and selectivity were determined by GC-FID using dodecane as an internal standard.

Table S3: Screening of various solvents

Entry	Solvents	Conversion / %		Selectivity / %		
		1a	2a	3a	3'a	4a+5a
1	<i>t</i> -Amyl alcohol	86	49	6	1	44
2	Toluene	82	54	2	1	43
3	Cyclohexane	96	38	4	1	57
4	2-Methyl THF	57	59	3	1	37
5	<i>p</i> -xylene	83	61	2	3	35
6	Methanol	100	13	-	-	6
7	THF	95	39	15	0.5	46
8	Dioxane	96	29	12	0.5	58

General reaction conditions: *General Procedure 1*, 1 mmol of **1a**, 200mg Raney Ni catalyst, a.q. NH₃ (25 wt%, 0.2 mL, 2.6 mmol), 180 °C, 3 mL *p*-xylene, 18h. Conversion and selectivity were determined by GC-FID using dodecane as an internal standard.

Table S4: Screening of the effect of different catalyst loading

Entry	Catalyst amount / mg	Conversion / %		Selectivity / %		
		1a	2a	3a	3'a	4a+5a

1	50	58	67	1	3	29
2	100	76	64	2	2	33
3	200	83	61	2	3	35
4	300	86	53	3	1	43
5	400	97	23	2	0	75

General reaction conditions: *General Procedure 1*, 1 mmol of **1a**, Raney Ni 2800 catalyst, a.q. NH₃ (25 wt%, 0.2 mL, 2.6 mmol), 180 °C, 3 mL *p*-xylene, 18h. Conversion and selectivity were determined by GC-FID using dodecane as an internal standard.

Table S5: Screening of the effect of various a.q. NH₃ amounts

Entry	Ammonia amount / mmol	Conversion / %			Selectivity / %		
		1a	2a	3a	3'a	4a+5a	
1	1.3	82	33	4	6	57	
2	2.6	83	61	2	3	35	
3	3.9	80	67	2	3	29	
4	5.2	80	74	1	3	23	
5	6.5	83	66	2	1	32	
6	7.8	81	65	2	1	32	

General reaction conditions: *General Procedure 1*, 1 mmol of **1a**, 200 mg of Raney Ni 2800 catalyst, a.q. NH₃ (25 wt%, 1.3-7.8 mmol (0.1-0.6 mL)), 180 °C, 3 mL *p*-xylene, 18h. Conversion and selectivity were determined by GC-FID using dodecane as an internal standard.

Table S6: Reaction temperature screening

Entry	Temperature / °C	Conversion / %			Selectivity / %		
		1a	2a	3a	3'a	4a+5a	
1	160	59	61	2	1	36	
2	170	73	59	2	1	38	
3	180	83	66	2	3	29	

General reaction conditions: *General Procedure 1*, 1 mmol of **1a**, 200 mg of Raney Ni 2800 catalyst, a.q. NH₃ (25 wt%, 0.2 mL, 2.6 mmol), 160-180 °C, 3 mL *p*-xylene, 18h. Conversion and selectivity were determined by GC-FID using dodecane as an internal standard.

Table S7: Reaction time screening

Entry	Reaction time / h	Conversion / %			Selectivity / %		
		1a	2a	3a	3'a	4a+5a	
1	2	33	33	0	2	65	
2	6	54	56	1	1	42	
3	8	62	52	2	1	46	
4	18	83	61	2	3	35	
5	24	90	50	3	1	47	

General reaction conditions: *General Procedure 1*, 1 mmol of **1a**, 200 mg of Raney Ni 2800 catalyst, a.q. NH₃ (25 wt%, 0.2 mL, 2.6 mmol), 180 °C, 3 mL *p*-xylene, 2-24h. Conversion and selectivity were determined by GC-FID using dodecane as an internal standard.

Table S8: Recycling test of the catalyst

Entry	Numbers	Conversion / %			Selectivity / %		
		1a	2a	3a	3'a	4a+5a	

1	1	83	61	2	3	35
2	2	73	74	1	5	20
3	3	67	74	1	5	20
4	4	67	64	1	5	31
5	5	65	77	1	6	16
6	6	66	70	1	5	24
7	7	70	63	0	5	32
8	8	65	78	1	6	16

General reaction conditions: *General Procedure 1*, 1 mmol of **1a**, 200 mg of Raney Ni 2800 catalyst, a.q. NH₃ (25 wt%, 0.2 mL, 2.6 mmol), 180 °C, 3 mL *p*-xylene, 18h. Conversion and selectivity were average value of three parallel reactions which were determined by GC-FID using dodecane as an internal standard.

Table S9: Direct synthesis of primary amines from vanillin alcohol and ammonia using Raney Ni as a catalyst.

Ammonia source	Conv., %	Sel., %					
		2m	5m	4m	6m	3'm	dimers
a.q. NH ₃ (25%) ^a	100	0	14	79	3	0	2
NH ₃ in dioxane ^b	97	1	29	66	3	3	1
NH ₃ in THF ^b	94	4	18	76	6	3	0
NH ₃ in MeOH ^b	100	0	26	74	0	0	0
(NH ₄) ₂ CO ₃	97	10	2	78	3	5	4
HCOONH ₄	100	0	1	63	0	0	0
NH ₄ H ₂ PO ₄	56	5	0	64	44	6	13
NH ₄ NO ₃	100	0	6	0	0	0	76
(NH ₄) ₂ HPO ₄	100	0	39	61	0	0	0
HCOONH ₄	100	0	14	79	3	0	6

General reaction conditions: *General Procedure 2*, 200 mg Raney Ni catalyst, 0.5 mmol substrate, 2 equivalent NH₃ in ammonia salts, 140°C, 18 h; conversion and selectivity were calculated by GC-FID. **a:** 0.4 mL a.q. NH₃, 3 mL *t*-amyl alcohol as solvent; **b:** Directly use 3 mL ammonia in dioxane (0.5M), THF (0.4M) or MeOH (7N) as both solvent and ammonia source.

Table S10: Direct synthesis of primary amines from vanillin alcohol and different ammonia sources using Ni/Al₂O₃-SiO₂ as a catalyst.

Ammonia source	Conv., %	Sel., %					
		2m	5m	4m	6m	3'm	dimers
a.q. NH ₃ (25%) ^a	100	5	5	81	0	0	9

NH ₃ in dioxane ^b	96	33	0	5	11	21	30
NH ₃ in THF ^b	96	11	0	9	0	34	45
(NH ₄) ₂ CO ₃	>99	45	1	4	1	22	27
(NH ₄) ₂ HPO ₄	98	15	1	9	14	18	43
HCOONH ₄	100	0	0	100	0	0	0

General reaction conditions: *General Procedure 2*, 200 mg Ni/Al₂O₃-SiO₂ catalyst, 0.5 mmol substrate, 2 equivalent NH₃ in ammonia salts, 140 °C, 18 h; conversion and selectivity were calculated by GC-FID. **a:** 0.4 mL a.q. NH₃, 3 mL *t*-amyl alcohol as solvent; **b:** directly use 3 mL ammonia in dioxane (0.5 M) or THF (0.4 M) as both solvent and ammonia source.

Table S11: Products distribution of direct synthesis of diamine from diol and a.q. NH₃ using Raney Ni as a catalyst.

Temperature / °C	a.q. NH ₃ / mL	Conv. / % 1u	Sel. / %				
			2u	3u	4u	5u	6u
180	1.0 ^a	>99	8	2	50	3	32
180	2.0	>99	61	4	9	2	7
180 ^b	2.0	81	62	1	3	3	4
170 ^b	2.0	73	61	<1	<1	2	<1
170	2.0	92	69	1	4	3	7
160	2.0	89	68	<1	<1	1	<1

General reaction conditions: *General Procedure 1*, 200 mg Raney Ni catalyst, 0.5 mmol 1,4-benzenedimethanol substrate, 2 mL a.q. NH₃ (25%), 2 mL *t*-amyl alcohol, **a:** 1 mL *t*-amyl alcohol and 3 mL a.q. NH₃, **b:** 0.5 mmol 1,3-benzenedimethanol as substrate; conversion and selectivity values were calculated by GC-FID.

Figure S1: Benzylamine production from benzyl alcohol with ammonia using various Raney Ni catalysts. General reaction conditions: *General Procedure 1*, benzyl alcohol **1a** (1 mmol), 3 mL *t*-amyl alcohol, 0.2 mL a.q. NH₃ (25% wt), 200 mg Raney Ni, 20 μL dodecane, 180 °C, 18h.

Figure S2: Typical GC-FID chromatogram of amination of benzyl alcohol with ammonia using Raney Ni, *p*-xylene as a solvent and dodecane as an internal standard.

Figure S3: Recycling test of the catalyst. **General reaction conditions:** *General Procedure 1*, benzyl alcohol (1 mmol), a.q. NH₃ (25 wt%, 0.2 mL), Raney Ni (200 mg), dodecane (internal standard, 20 μL), 3 mL *p*-xylene, 180 °C, 18h.

Products distribution:

Figure S4: Products distribution of the amination reaction between *p*-hydroxybenzyl alcohol and ammonia and MS chromatograms of the possible dimers. **General reaction condition:** *General Procedure 1*, 1 mmol substrate, 200 mg Raney Ni, 3mL *t*-amyl alcohol, 0.4 mL a.q. NH₃ (25%), 180 °C, 24h.

Products distribution:

Figure S5: Products distribution of the amination reaction between vanillyl alcohol and ammonia and MS chromatograms of the possible dimers (d1-d5). **General reaction condition:** *General Procedure 1*, 1mmol substrate, 200 mg Raney Ni, 3mL *tert*-amyl alcohol, 0.4mL a.q. NH₃(25%),

180 °C, 24 h.

Figure S6: Dimerization of vanillyl alcohol under basic conditions as proposed by Dimmel et.al.³ showing the quinonemethide structure. The pathway shows the easy loss of oxygen from benzyl alcohol para to phenol.

Note 4 to Figure S5 and Figure S6: according to our observations and previous reports,^{3,4} the formed quinonemethide intermediate could dimerize with the vanillyl alcohol, as well as hydrogenolysis and/or decarbonylation by-products (**Figure 3**, pathway 1-3) forming bisphenol structures with a molecular weight of 260 (**Figure 3**, **d1**, **d4** and **d5**) or other structure with a molecular weight of 274 (**d2**). Another possible bisphenol (**d3**) is formed by self-condensation of vanillin.

Figure S7: Mass spectrometry chromatograms of the synthesized *p*-xylylenediamine and *m*-xylylenediamine.

3. Spectral data of isolated compounds

4-Methylbenzylamine Hydrochloride (2b)

The compound was synthesized according to the *General procedure 1* using *p*-tolylmethanol (129 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **2b** (93 mg, 56% yield) as a white solid. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 7.35 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 2H), 7.24 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 2H), 4.07 (s, 2H), 2.34 (s, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 141.56, 132.67, 132.01, 131.30, 45.40, 22.50. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₈H₁₂N [M+H]⁺: 122.09697; found: 122.09636. The spectral data are identical to the previously reported.⁵

4-*tert*-Butylbenzylamine Hydrochloride (2c)

The compound was synthesized according to the *General procedure 1* using (4-(*tert*-butyl)phenyl)methanol (173 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **2c** (147 mg, 70% yield) as a slightly yellow solid. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 7.48 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 7.40 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 4.09 (s, 2H), 1.31 (s, 9H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 152.09, 130.08, 128.46, 125.70, 42.66, 34.14, 30.30. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₁H₁₈N [M+H]⁺: 164.14392; found: 164.14337.

2-Methylbenzylamine Hydrochloride (2d)

The compound was synthesized according to the *General procedure 1* using piperonyl alcohol (62 mg, 0.5 mmol) to afford **2d** (36 mg, 44% yield) as a white solid. **¹H NMR** (600 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 7.35 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H), 7.27-7.21 (m, 3H), 4.12 (s, 2H), 2.37 (s, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 136.71, 131.21, 130.52, 128.90, 128.85, 126.31, 40.13, 17.65. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₈H₁₂N [M+H]⁺: 122.09627; found: 122.09643. The spectral data are identical to the previously reported.⁶

Piperonylamine Hydrochloride (2g)

The compound was synthesized according to the *General procedure 1* using piperonyl alcohol (77 mg, 0.5 mmol) to afford **2g** (55 mg, 58% yield) as a light-yellow solid. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 6.96-6.92 (m, 2H), 6.86 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 5.98 (s, 2H), 4.02 (s, 2H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 151.10, 150.94, 129.16, 125.36, 111.45, 110.88, 104.15, 45.49. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₈H₁₀NO₂ [M+H]⁺: 152.07115; found: 152.07053. The spectral data are identical to the previously reported.⁶

4-(trifluoromethyl)benzylamine Hydrochloride (2h)

The compound was synthesized according to the *General procedure 1* using piperonyl alcohol (176 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **2h** (102 mg, 48% yield) as a white solid. **¹H NMR** (600 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 7.77 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 2H), 7.70 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 2H), 4.25 (s, 2H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 137.39, 130.78 (q, *J*_{C-F} = 33.2 Hz), 129.37, 125.61 (q, *J*_{C-F} = 3.8 Hz), 123.99 (q, *J*_{C-F} = 271.5 Hz), 42.30. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₈H₉F₃N [M+H]⁺: 176.06808; found: 176.06816. The spectral data are identical to the previously reported.⁷

3-(trifluoromethyl)benzylamine Hydrochloride (2i)

The compound was synthesized according to the *General procedure 1* using piperonyl alcohol (176 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **2i** (109 mg, 50% yield) as a light-yellow solid. **¹H NMR** (600 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 7.75 (s, 1H), 7.66 (dd, *J* = 18.0 Hz, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 7.56 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 1H), 4.14 (s, 2H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 134.34, 132.59, 130.96 (q, *J*_{C-F} = 32.6 Hz), 129.70, 125.52 (q, *J*_{C-F} = 1.8 Hz), 123.93 (q, *J*_{C-F} = 271.6 Hz), 42.34. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₈H₉F₃N [M+H]⁺: 176.06787; found: 176.06816.

4-Methoxybenzylamine Hydrochloride (2j)

The compound was synthesized according to the *General procedure 1* using (4-methoxyphenyl)methanol (151 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **2j** (130 mg, 69% yield) as a light yellow solid. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 7.40 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.97 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.05 (s, 2H), 3.80 (s, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 160.43, 130.24, 124.89, 114.11, 54.45, 42.53. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₈H₁₂NO [M+H]⁺: 138.09189; found: 138.09128. The spectral data are identical to the previously reported.⁵

3,4-Dimethoxybenzylamine Hydrochloride (2k)

The compound was synthesized according to the *General procedure 1* using (3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)methanol (176 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **2k** (120 mg, 56% yield) as a light yellow solid. **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 7.09 (d, *J* = 1.6 Hz, 1H), 7.03-6.97 (m, 2H), 4.05 (s, 2H), 3.86 (s, 3H), 3.83 (s, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 149.87, 149.47, 125.48, 121.59, 112.37, 111.71, 55.18, 42.86. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₉H₁₄NO₂ [M+H]⁺: 168.10245; found: 168.10186.

Vanillylamine (2m)

The compound was synthesized according to the *General procedure 2* using vanillyl alcohol (78 mg, 0.5 mmol) to afford **2m** (30 mg, 40% yield) as a light-yellow solid. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CD_3OD): δ 6.97 (d, $J = 1.2$ Hz, 1H), 6.82-6.76 (m, 2H), 3.86 (s, 3H), 3.82 (s, 2H). $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (101 MHz, CD_3OD): δ 150.49, 148.94, 131.58, 123.34, 117.64, 114.17, 57.65, 46.72. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, m/z) calculated for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{10}\text{NO}_2$ $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 154.08233; found: 154.08621. The spectral data are identical to the previously reported.⁸

Cyclopentylamine Hydrochloride (2q)

The compound was synthesized according to the *General procedure 1* using cyclopentanol (88 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **2q** (42 mg, 37% yield) as a white solid. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (600 MHz, CD_3OD): δ 3.59 (p, $J = 6.6$ Hz, 1H), 2.10-2.05 (m, 2H), 1.85-1.79 (m, 2H), 1.72-1.60 (m, 4H). $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (151 MHz, CD_3OD): δ 53.33, 32.05, 24.90. The spectral data are identical to the previously reported.⁹

1-octylamine Hydrochloride (2r)

The compound was synthesized according to the *General procedure 1* using 1-octanol (130 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **2r** (68 mg, 41% yield) as a white solid. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (600 MHz, CD_3OD): δ 2.93-2.90 (m, 2H), 1.66 (p, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 2H), 1.42-1.32 (m, 10H), 0.91 (t, $J = 6.6$ Hz, 3H). $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (151 MHz, CD_3OD): δ 40.79, 32.89, 30.19, 30.18, 28.58, 27.47, 23.68, 14.40. The spectral data are identical to the previously reported.¹⁰

1-dodecylamine Hydrochloride (2s)

The compound was synthesized according to the *General procedure 1* using 1-dodecanol (87 mg, 0.5 mmol) to afford **2s** (49 mg, 47% yield) as a white solid. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (600 MHz, CD_3OD): δ 2.93-2.90 (m, 2H), 1.66 (p, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 2H), 1.43-1.30 (m, 18H), 0.90 (t, $J = 6.6$ Hz, 3H). $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (151 MHz, CD_3OD): δ 40.78, 33.06, 30.74, 30.73, 30.65, 30.50, 30.46, 30.23, 28.56, 27.47, 23.72, 14.45. The spectral data are identical to the previously reported.¹¹

4. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra

Supplementary Figure S8. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR of compound 2b.

Supplementary Figure S9. ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 2c.

Supplementary Figure S10. ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 2d.

Supplementary Figure S11. ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 2g.

Supplementary Figure S12. ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 2h.

Supplementary Figure S13. ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 2i.

Supplementary Figure S14. ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 2j.

Supplementary Figure S15. ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 2k.

Supplementary Figure S16. ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 2m.

Supplementary Figure S17. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR of compound **2q**.

Supplementary Figure S18. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR of compound **2r**.

Supplementary Figure S19. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR of compound 2s.

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